

Thermal evaporation technique to prepare ZrO₂ doped TiO₂ thin film on Si Substrate

^{1,2} A. Mohamed Saleem, S. Nivetha^{1,3}, K. Kaviyarasu^{4,5}, **A. Ayeshamariam**^{1,3*}, N. Punithavelan⁶ and M. Jayachandran⁷

¹Research and Development Centre, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli – 620 024, India

²Department of Physics, Jamal Mohamed College (Auto), Thiruchirappalli – 620 020, India

³Department of Physics, Khadir Mohideen College, Adirampattinam - 614701, India

⁴UNESCO-UNISA Africa Chair in Nanoscience's/Nanotechnology Laboratories, College of Graduate Studies, University of South Africa (UNISA), Muckleneuk Ridge, P O Box 392, Pretoria, South Africa

⁵Nanosciences African network (NANOAFNET), Materials Research Group (MRG), iThemba LABS-National Research Foundation (NRF), 1 Old Faure Road, 7129, P. O. Box 722, Somerset West, Western Cape Province, South Africa

⁶School of Advanced Sciences in Physics, Vellore Institute of Technology, Chennai Campus, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

⁷Department of Physics, Sethu Institute of Technology, Pullor, Kariyapatti, Tamil Nadu

Email: aismma786@gmail.com

Abstract

ZrO₂ and TiO₂ has much attention among the nanomaterials because of good compatibility of technological and biological activities. The two gram of Titanium isopropoxide ((Ti(OCH)(CH₃)₂)₄) is mixed in 25 ml of water to prepare 1 M solution. Similarly 0.9 gm of ZrO₂ mixed with 15 ml of water to get 0.5 M solution. By using simple co-precipitation technique powder particle was prepared. This powdered particle was pelletized and then used it for target. It was allowed to raise the temperature up to 200°C for 15 minutes. This pellet was evaporated by using this technique on Si substrate, it was characterised by using X-Ray diffractometers to study the analysis were performed to study the structural and optical properties. In XRD analysis some of the sharp peaks were observed and identified the presence of TiO₂ doped with ZrO₂ which is suggested the good crystallinity. This sample was used to measure the conductivity and resistivity of the prepared sample.

Keywords; Si substrate, Titanium isopropoxide, ZrO₂ and Thermal evaporation

References

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